

Pathogenesis of knee osteoarthritis in obese patients: mechanical overload and molecular mechanisms

Patogenia de la osteoartritis de rodilla en pacientes obesos: sobrecarga mecánica y mecanismos moleculares

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Abstract

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a frequent comorbidity in obese patients, which significantly impacts their quality of life and represents a common cause of disability. The pathogenesis of OA is often related to overuse and mechanical overload, which are markedly present in obese patients. However, this approximation oversimplifies the complex metabolic and inflammatory pathways connecting obesity and OA. Indeed, other frequent obesity comorbidities like diabetes, hypertension, and metabolic syndrome are closely related to OA. Moreover, low-grade chronic inflammation, an obesity hallmark, is associated with articular cartilage damage through several pathways. Furthermore, mechanical overload is a mechanism that depends on several molecular pathways. From the role

of mechanosensitive receptors to the induction of proinflammatory cytokines, the degeneration of articular cartilage in OA is highly dependent on inflammatory pathways. Understanding the pathophysiology of OA allows for the inclusion of new therapeutic targets. Nevertheless, more research is needed to properly comprehend the pathophysiology of OA and to implement new strategies accordingly. This review aims to analyze the molecular mechanisms associated with mechanical overload and their participation in the origin of OA; likewise, other mechanisms associated with obesity will also be reviewed.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, obesity, overweight, inflammation, metabolic syndrome.

La osteoartritis (OA) es una comorbilidad frecuente en pacientes obesos, que afecta significativamente su calidad de vida y representa una causa común de discapacidad. La patogénesis de la OA suele estar relacionada con la sobrecarga mecánica, factores marcadamente presentes en los pacientes obesos. Sin embargo, esta aproximación simplifica en exceso las complejas vías metabólicas e inflamatorias que conectan la obesidad con la OA. De hecho, otras comorbilidades frecuentes de la obesidad, como la diabetes, la hipertensión y el síndrome metabólico, están estrechamente relacionadas con la OA. Además, la inflamación crónica de bajo grado, un sello distintivo de la obesidad, está asociada con el daño del cartílago articular a través de varias vías. Por otro lado, la sobrecarga mecánica es un mecanismo que depende de varias vías moleculares. Desde el papel de los receptores mecanosensibles hasta la inducción de citocinas proinflamatorias, la degeneración del cartílago articular en la OA depende en gran medida de las vías inflamatorias. Comprender la fisiopatología de la OA permite incluir nuevos objetivos terapéuticos. No obstante, se necesita más investigación para comprender adecuadamente la fisiopatología de la OA y aplicar nuevas estrategias en consecuencia. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo analizar los mecanismos moleculares asociados con la sobrecarga mecánica y su participación en el origen de la OA; asimismo, se revisarán otros mecanismos asociados con la obesidad.

Palabras clave: Osteoartritis, obesidad, sobrepeso, inflamación, síndrome metabólico.

Obesity is a disease characterized by a positive energetic balance resulting in increased fat deposits and, thus, higher body mass index (BMI). Conventionally, overweight is defined as a BMI of 25 or higher, and obesity as a BM of 30 or higher¹. The prevalence of obesity has increased worldwide in the past 50 years, reaching pandemic levels. Since 1985, it has shown a steady up-trend in prevalence in adults and children². Recent studies with millions of participants have stated that the overall prevalence of obesity is about 40%, with some variations depending on the country analyzed³. Globally, the combined prevalence of overweight and obesity has risen by 28% for adults and 47% for children. In absolute terms, the number of individuals with a BMI higher than 25 has increased from 921 million in 1980 to 2.1 billion in 2013⁴.

Furthermore, in 2017 nearly 4.7 million deaths were attributable to high BMI in men and women; and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) directly related to obesity or its comorbidities have risen to over 140 million⁵. Obesity represents a healthcare challenge because of its close relationship with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2), fatty liver disease, hypertension (HT), myocardial infarction, stroke, obstructive sleep apnea, osteoarthritis (OA), and several cancers⁶. However, the estimation of healthcare costs associated with obesity is somewhat inaccurate. Few studies have provided a complete analysis of obesity and the burden of the associated clinical spectrum⁷. Considering healthcare costs, lost productivity, and the burden of associated comorbidities, the global economic impact of obesity has been estimated to be US\$ 2 trillion or nearly 3% of the global gross domestic product⁸.

OA is a particularly underestimated comorbidity of obesity, as it does not represent an immediate lethal threat. However, OA significantly decreases patients' quality of life (QoL), and its prevalence is considerably higher among obese patients. Moreover, OA significantly contributes to DALYs in obese patients, mainly because of mechanical limitations and severe pain^{9,10}. The pathogenesis of OA may appear straightforward, given that joint mechanical overload and overuse are the most acknowledged mechanisms. However, this is an oversimplification of the pathogenesis of OA, as that several molecular mechanisms inherent to the mechanical overload or the obesity itself also participate in the origin of this pathology¹¹. This review aims to analyze the molecular mechanisms associated with mechanical overload and their participation in the origin of OA; likewise, other mechanisms associated with obesity will also be reviewed.

PATHOGENESIS OF OSTEOARTHRITIS: MORE THAN JUST JOINT OVERLOAD

OA is the most common chronic degenerative joint disease, and one of the leading causes of limited joint mobility and disability in the elderly¹². The principal pathological change in OA is the destruction of articular cartilage, including chondrocyte apoptosis and extracellular matrix (ECM) degradation, and bone remodeling. When subjected to acute or long-term abnormal mechanical loads, articular cartilage lacks regenerative properties. The specific mechanism of mechanical load-induced OA is yet to be revealed¹³. It has been reported that mechanical overload activates a plethora of inflammatory pathways such as interleukin 1 β (IL-1 β), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), Wnt, and oxidative stress pathways. All of these pathways are involved in the regulation of joint inflammation, activation of metalloproteinases (MMPs), and aggrecanases (ADAMTs), chondrocyte apoptosis, and ECM degradation, ultimately generating OA¹⁴.

Mechanical stress and overload are detected in articular cartilage through mechanical receptors of heterogeneous natures. For instance, integrin detects mechanical signals in ECM and activates a FAK-MAPK axis to upregulate proinflammatory factors like MMPs, ADAMTs, and IL-6¹⁵. Hirose et al.¹⁶ showed that integrin inhibition resulted in the downregulation of IL-1 β , TNF- α , MMPs, and MAPK-associated pathways, significantly improving the OA inflammatory profile. Likewise, ion channels also play a role in mechanical signal transduction. The mechanosensitive ion channel transient receptor potential channel 4 (TRPV4) of chondrocytes increases the extracellular Ca⁺⁺ influx, therefore, upregulating fas-related proteins and all the caspases related to chondrocyte apoptosis¹⁷. While these mechanisms partly explain the progressive worsening of OA, the downstream signaling related to cytokines and inflammatory pathways represents the most significant proportion of the pathogenesis of this disease^{18,19}.

Firstly, IL-1 β is significantly overexpressed in OA chondrocytes compared to normal chondrocytes²⁰. In vitro studies have demonstrated that stimulation through mechanical overloading results in significant upregulation of IL-1 β expression²¹. Downstream signaling of IL-1 β implicates several pathways involved in the progression of OA. For instance, higher IL-1 β concentrations in the joint correlate with higher expression of the inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), which increases nitric oxide (NO) concentrations and causes oxidative stress^{22,23}. Moreover, IL-1 β activates all MAPK-related pathways, resulting in increased expression of matrix-degrading enzymes like MMP1, MMP3, ADAMT4, ADAMT5, and many others²⁴. In turn, these activate other proinflammatory factors such as cyclooxygenase 2 (COX-2), iNOS, and IL-6. Consequently, this increased expression of ECM-degrading enzymes directly translates to irreversible cartilage damage²⁵.

In this scenario, the TNF- α pathway has also been reported to be activated in patients with OA²⁶. This pathway is activated by an excessive mechanical load in vivo and in vitro, triggering downstream inflammatory, proapoptotic, and ECM degradation pathways²⁷. Experimental studies have demonstrated that TNF- α directly induces apoptosis, increases the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and activates ECM-degrading enzymes like MMP1, MMP13, and ADAMT4^{28,29}. Furthermore, evidence shows that the TNF- α pathway further upregulated IL-1 β expression, forming a positive feedback loop between these signaling pathways³⁰. Likewise, TNF- α activates other inflammatory pathways like MAPK and the c-jun pathway, and indirectly activates other ECM-degrading enzymes like ADAMT9, responsible for articular cartilage degradation³¹. To further support this theory, other authors have reported that after inhibiting the TNF- α pathway in chondrocytes, there was significant downregulation of inflammatory factors in articular cartilage, resulting in less ECM degradation and chondrocyte apoptosis³².

Another important signaling pathway involved in OA progression is the Wnt/ β -Catenin signaling pathway, which IL-1 β directly activates³³. Increased expression of the Wnt1-inducible-signaling pathway protein (WISP-1) is found in both murine and human OA models. Moreover, WISP-1 increases articular cartilage degradation by upregulating the expression of MMPs and ADAMTs in chondrocytes and local macrophages³⁴. However, the understanding of the participation of the Wnt pathway in OA progression remains incomplete. Increased articular cartilage destruction has been reported in mice, with increased expression of the Wnt pathway antagonist dickkopf WNT signaling pathway inhibitor 1 (DKK1). Similarly, Theologis et al.³⁵ found that DKK1 levels were upregulated in patients with OA, showing a positive correlation with OA severity. Therefore, more research is needed to further elucidate this pathway's role.

Considering this amalgamation of mechanisms, it is evident that people with high BMI have a significantly greater risk of OA than the general population. Obesity results in mechanical overload of the joints, triggering all the mechanisms abovementioned^{11,36}. However, the connection between obesity and OA is beyond the "wear-and-tear" of cartilage. Obesity is closely related to increased systemic inflammation³⁷; moreover, population-based studies have linked obesity to HT, DM, dyslipidemia, and other metabolic components strongly correlated with OA, radiographic changes, pain severity, and functional score impairment³⁸. The microenvironment of "sick" adipose tissue in obese patients excels in proinflammatory cytokine production, thus resulting in increased levels of circulating molecules like IL-1 β , leptin, and TNF- α ³⁹.

Leptin levels are significantly increased in obese patients, and chondrocytes express a significant amount of receptors for this molecule⁴⁰. Along these lines, leptin binds to its receptor Ob-Rb, and another homologous

receptor (GP130), activating the transcription factor STAT3¹¹. Activation of STAT3 increases the transcription of the SOCS3 genes, thus increasing the expression of MMPs, iNOS, ADAMTs, and several proinflammatory cytokines^{41,42}. Less is known about the role of adiponectin in joint disease since both proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory properties have been reported⁴³. Recent studies have reported that weight loss is associated with decreased circulating levels of leptin and increased availability of adiponectin, resulting in decreased disease activity. The latter suggests that benefits from weight loss are not only due to decreased mechanical load, but also associated with the improvement in the cytokine and adipokine profiles^{44,45}.

OA is a frequent comorbidity in obese patients, which significantly decreases their QoL and represents a common cause of disability. The pathogenesis of OA is often related to overuse and mechanical overload. In the case of obese patients, both pathways are equally present. However, this approximation oversimplifies the complex metabolic and inflammatory pathways connecting obesity and OA. Indeed, other frequent obesity comorbidities like DM, HT, and metabolic syndrome are closely related to OA. Moreover, low-grade chronic inflammation, an obesity hallmark, is associated with articular cartilage damage through several pathways. Furthermore, mechanical overload depends on several molecular pathways. From the role of mechanosensitive receptors to the induction of proinflammatory cytokines, it is safe to say that the “wear-and-tear” conception of OA is highly dependent of inflammatory pathways. Understanding the pathophysiology of OA allows for the inclusion of new therapeutic targets. Nevertheless, more research is needed to properly comprehend the pathophysiology of OA and to implement new strategies accordingly.

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